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7-2-2021

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., Priyanka and Chakravarty, Rupak, "Measuring Patent-Citations of LIS Literature: An analytical study of the Journal Scientometrics" (2021). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 5954.
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Measuring Patent-Citations of LIS Literature: An analytical study of the Journal Scientometrics

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to analyse the utility and application of Library and Information Science (LIS) research in patents representing innovations, inventions and new knowledge. With this research, we have tried to bridge a gap between LIS research and patents, which is unavailable till date in literature. To conduct the study, various patent search databases were used. Data in the form of DOIs were extracted from Scopus database for the journal Scientometrics and were processed and analysed in visualisation software and spreadsheet software. The findings reveals how industries filing patents derive valuable inputs from LIS research in terms of its utilization, recognition and acceptance. This research paper will enhance the understanding regarding LIS, what is its value in Research and Development (R&D). Normally, it is believed that only STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Medical) research is fruitful for patents and innovations. The study breaks the glass ceiling as it provides an evidence based approach to justify the LIS research does play a crucial role in growth, development and progress of the society through its existence and proven integration with the patents. The findings reveal that LIS research is influencing Patents as they are being cited regularly with the growth in this discipline.

Key words- Patent citation, citation, cite score, citing patent, cited articles, Scientometrics, DOIs.

1. Introduction:

A patent application involves claims regarding the novelty of an innovation and these claims are often supported and demarcated by references to other documents. Foremost such references refer to previously granted patents, but other documents, including scientific papers also play an important role (Björn Hammarfelt, 2021). Patent citation analysis comprises a larger area of study including analyses of “patent to patent citations” and citation links between patents and papers, where especially the economic value of the cited patent in relation to citations received has been studied (Trajtenberg, 1990). In past, patent citations have been used to forecast the success of products, especially medicines (Windsor, 1979). Moreover, patent citations have also

been studied in relation to patent litigation (Malaspina, 2019). They represent a ‘paper trail’ of the knowledge flows between citing and cited inventors, although, as pointed out by Jaffe and Trajtenberg in 2002. They indicate which parts of the knowledge described are claimed in the patent and which parts have been claimed by previous patents or non-patent (Jaffe Adam B., 2017). They used to measure invention value and knowledge flow. Patent citation shows the growth in inventions. Citations in patents are the results of a highly mediated process that involves multiple parties: the inventor, the patent attorney and the patent examiner (Meyer, 2000). The important manifesto for research on R&D and productivity growth, suggested that the frequency with which patents from different industries cite each other is the reason for the R&D. The citation is a reference of information used in research by patent.

2. Study Scope and Objectives:

Library and information science (LIS) is a very broad discipline, which uses a wide range of constantly evolving research strategies and techniques. The study aims to assess the value of LIS research in patents and innovation. It aims to track and link scholarly articles that are cited in patents, and examine the citing patents. The specific objectives are:

- (i) To investigate the application and usage of LIS research in Patents.
- (ii) To identify the influential research papers in LIS which are being cited by patents.
- (iii) To identify the top authors of LIS who are being cited by the patents.
- (iv) To examine the fields/domains of patents citing LIS research.

3. Research Design:

The study identified scholarly articles and the corresponding patents influenced by them. For the purpose of testing LIS literature the journal *Scientometrics* (published by Springer Nature) (ISSN:0138-9130E-ISSN:1588-286) was chosen. It is an International Journal with global outreach for all Quantitative Aspects of the Science of Science, Communication in Science and Science Policy. (Scientometrics, 2021). The journal is concerned with the quantitative features and characteristics of science and scientific research. Its Scopus coverage years is from 1978 to present. A data set of 5651 *Scientometrics* article DOIs were retrieved and extracted from Scopus (the largest abstracting/indexing and citation database providing access to reliable data, metrics and analytical tools) as a CSV file. DOI, or Digital Object Identifier, is a string of numbers, letters and symbols used to permanently identify an article or document and link to it on the web. The exported file was cleansed for DOIs accuracy. The patent citation data was

retrieved from the global patent databases like Google Patents, Patentscope (WIPO) in general and jurisdiction-specific patent databases including USPTO Web Patent Database (<https://www.uspto.gov/patents/search>), China National Intellectual Property Administration (<http://pss-system.cnipa.gov.cn/sipopublicsearch/inportal/i18n.shtml>), Korea European Patent Office (<https://www.epo.org/>). Citations for the research papers were retrieved from the database including Free Patents Online (FPO) (<https://www.freepatentsonline.com/>) and WIPO's Patentscope (<https://patentscope.wipo.int/search/en/search.jsf>).

4. Results and Discussion:

4.1 Cite Score Analysis:

In Scopus the search was made under the title “Scientometrics” journal. (<https://www.scopus.com/sources>) this is done to study the important metrics related to this journal including “cite score”. This journal falls under three different subject’s categories with different ranks and percentile as mentioned in the table 1.

Table 1. Scientometrics categories

Category (Subject Areas)	Rank	Percentile
Social Sciences: General Social Sciences	#13/260	95 th
Social Sciences: Library and Information Sciences	#21/235	91 st
Computer Science: Computer Science Applications	#166/693	76 th

The subject category social science is further divided into general social science and LIS which scored the rank 13/260 and 21/235 with 95 and 91 percentiles, respectively. Whereas percentile is a value on a scale of 100 that indicates the percent of a distribution that is equal to or below it. CiteScore is a metric for measuring journal impact in Scopus. The calculation of CiteScore for the current year is based on the number of citations received by a journal in the latest 4 years (including the calculation year), divided by the number of documents published by the journal in those four years (Fig.1).

The journal cite score was found to be 5.6 in the year (2019) and 5.2 for the year (2020) with 7,079 citations received (2017- 2020) and 1,349 total documents published within same time interval. Cited percentage was 76% with source normalized impact per paper (SNIP) of 1.565. SCImago Journal Rank (SJR) was 0.999 and 4.0 as CiteScoreTracker (June 2021). In 2019 the impact factor of scientometric journal was 2.867 and its five-year impact factor was 3.073. The total number of articles downloaded till 2020 were 1,089,258.

Fig. 1. Scientometrics CiteScore and CiteScore Tracker.

Table 2 depicts the source title and their corresponding cite score and percentile for the year 2020. The first rank was given to journal of industrial ecology with 12.8 citeScore and 99 percentiles whereas scientometrics hold 13 rank with 5.2 CiteScore and 95 percentiles.

Table 2. Current source rank and titles

Current Source Rank	Source title	CiteScore 2020	Percentile
#1	Journal of Industrial Ecology	12.8	99 th
#2	Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability	11.7	99 th
#3	Journal of Social Issues	8.2	99 th
#4	Social Science Computer Review	7.2	98 th
#5	Human Relations	7.1	98 th
#6	Regional Studies	7.0	97 th
#7	Social Studies of Science	6.6	97 th

#8	Policy Sciences	6.3	97 th
#9	Sociological Science	5.9	96 th
#10	Design Studies	5.8	96 th
#11	Social Networks	5.8	95 th
#12	City, Culture and Society	5.5	95 th
#13	Scientometrics	5.2	95th

Figure 2 represents the number of documents published has been during 2011-2021. The overall growth rate of publication is positive with only one downfall in 2019 and in 2020 it reached the peak which witnessed highest productivity. From the trend it is observed that the number of articles published has been increased with time. Further, the CiteScore was analyzed for the time interval 2011-2021 which shows positively growth trend. The CiteScore increases gradually with time (Fig.3).

Fig. 2. Documents published in Scientometrics last few years (2011-2021).

Fig. 3. CiteScore of last ten years (2011-2020).

4.2 Patent Analysis:

CSV file containing 5651 DOIs of research published in Scientometrics journal obtained from Scopus was imported into Lens analyser interface for further analysis (Fig 4 a, b). It was found that, out of 5651 DOIs, added 37 papers (query articles cited in patent literature (QNPL) were found to be cited by 62 patents. (Fig. 4c). Out of 62 citing patents, 44 were granted, 13 were having application status. The same DOI dataset in Lens Patent 2.O (8.0 Beta), produced 39 QNPL with 2 additional results (17 and 30) Table 3. The sum of citing patents for all patent-cited scholarly works in the result set was found to be 70 whereas and the unique count of patents that cite scholarly work was 59 (Fig 4).

4.2.1 LIS Research Cited by Patents:

Fig.4. (a) Patent Analysis of "Scientometrics" Journal (b). Patent analysis result (c). Patent analysis of scientometrics journal result.

Table 3. Cited articles

S.No.	Title	Publication Year	Author/s	Length of paper	Citing Patents Count	Citing Works Count
1.	Threaded Email Messages in Self-Organization and Science & Technology Studies Oriented Mailing Lists	2000	Andrés Zelman; Loet Leydesdorff	19	11	11
2.	A microscopic link analysis of academic institutions within a country — the case of Israel	2004	Judit Bar-Ilan	12	7	81
3.	A quantitative analysis of indicators of scientific performance	2008	Sune Lehmann; Andrew D. Jackson; Benny Lautrup	21	4	87
4.	Agent-based computing from multi-agent systems to agent-based models: a visual survey	2011	Muaz A. Niazi; Amir Hussain	20	3	221
5.	Co-word maps of biotechnology: An example of cognitive scientometrics	1984	Arie Rip; Jean Pierre Courtial	19	3	232

6.	A hybrid mapping of information science	2008	Frizo Janssens; Wolfgang Glänzel; Bart De Moor	24	2	81
7.	A study of scientometric methods to identify emerging technologies via modeling of milestones	2012	Robert K. Abercrombie; Akaninyene W. Udoeyop; Bob G Schlicher	15	2	25
8.	Hypothesis generation guided by co-word clustering	2003	Johannes Stegmann; Guenter Grohmann	24	2	87
9.	Measures for textual patent similarities: a guided way to select appropriate approaches	2010	Martin G. Moehrle	14	2	47
10.	Negative results are disappearing from most disciplines and countries	2011	Daniele Fanelli	13	2	598
11.	Accuracy of inter-researcher similarity measures based on topical and social clues	2011	Guillaume Cabanac	23	2	29
12.	Discovery of factors influencing patent value based on machine learning in patents in the field of nanotechnology	2009	Scott D. Bass; Lukasz Kurgan	24	2	31
13.	Cluster analysis of bibliographic references as a scientometric method	1989	J. T. Sharabchiev	10	2	10
14.	Bibliometric mapping of science in a policy context	2001	Ed C. M. Noyons	15	1	98
15.	Anticipating technological breakthroughs: Using bibliographic coupling to explore the nanotubes paradigm	2007	Osmo Kuusi; Martin Meyer	18	1	51
16.	Random thoughts on citationology its theory and practice	1998	Eugene Garfield	7	1	86
17.	'Mini small worlds' of shortest link paths crossing domain boundaries in an academic Web space	2006	Lennart Björneborn	19	1	32
18.	A SCI-Map case study: Building a map of AIDS research	1994	Henry Small	12	1	57
19.	Recommending research collaborations using link prediction and random forest	2014	Raf Guns; Ronald Rousseau	12	1	39

	classifiers					
20.	Separating the articles of authors with the same name	2007	José M. Soler	9	1	46
21.	DeepPatent: patent classification with convolutional neural networks and word embedding	2018	Shaobo Li; Jie Hu; Yuxin Cui; Jianjun Hu	23	1	40
22.	Evaluations of context-based co-citation searching	2012	Masaki Eto	22	1	35
23.	Co-author inclusion: A novel recursive algorithmic method for dealing with homonyms in bibliometric analysis	2006	Steven Wooding; Kate Wilcox-Jay; Grant Lewison; Jonathan Grant	10	1	34
24.	National characteristics in international scientific co-authorship relations	2001	Wolfgang Glänzel	46	1	524
25.	Prediction of emerging technologies based on analysis of the US patent citation network	2012	Péter Érdi; Kinga Makovi; Zoltán Somogyvári; Katherine J. Strandburg; Jan Tobochnik; Péter Volf; László Zalányi	17	1	140
26.	Patent citations in a novel field of technology: What can they tell about interactions between emerging communities of science and technology?	2000	Martin Meyer	27	1	104
27.	Authorship patterns in Dutch sociology	1997	J. de Haan	11	1	23
28.	On the possibility and reliability of predictions based on stochastic citation processes	1997	Wolfgang Glänzel	11	1	24
29.	Sections-based bibliographic coupling for research paper recommendation	2019	Raja Habib; Muhammad Afzal	13	1	16
30.	Mapping library and information science in China: a coauthorship network analysis	2009	Erjia Yan; Ying Ding; Qinghua Zhu	16	1	66
31.	Similarity measures for document mapping: A comparative study on the level of an individual scientist	2008	Christian Sternitzke; Isumo Bergmann	17	1	75

32.	Collaboration and Cognitive Structures in Social Science Research Fields. Towards Socio-Cognitive Analysis in Information Systems	2001	Peter Mutschke; Anabel Quan Haase	15	1	35
33.	Methods for using patents in cross-country comparisons	2002	Éric Archambault	15	1	45
34.	Bibliometric fingerprints: name disambiguation based on approximate structure equivalence of cognitive maps	2010	Li Tang; John P. Walsh	21	1	96
35.	Reference standards for citation based assessments	1993	András Schubert; Tibor Braun	14	1	51
36.	Improving the functionality of interactive bibliometric science maps	2001	R.K. Buter; Ed C. M. Noyons	13	1	15
37.	Unsupervised author disambiguation using Dempster---Shafer theory	2014	Hao Wu; Bo Li; Yijian Pei; Jun He	17	1	35
38.	Clustering the science citation index using co-citations. II. Mapping science	1985	H. Small; E. Sweeney; E. Greenlee	19	1	119
39.	Mapping the backbone of science	2005	Kevin W. Boyack; Richard Klavans; Katy Börner	23	1	629
			Average	17.44		
			Total	680	70	

Table 3 depicts all of the patent-cited articles with associated details like author(s), publication year etc. The highest citing patent count is 11 for the paper titled "Threaded Email Messages in Self-Organization and Science & Technology Studies Oriented Mailing Lists" published in 2000. It was followed by citing patent count 7, 4, 3, etc., credited to papers focusing on diverse research areas. It is interesting to note that the LIS literature published in the journal *Scientometrics* are continually being cited by the patents. The article "Sections-based bibliographic coupling for research paper recommendation", published in 2019 was cited by a patent in same year i.e., 2019.

4.2.3 Citing Patents

A total of 59 unique count of patents that cite scholarly works were retrieved in the result set whereas the sum of citing patents for all patent-cited scholarly works in the result set was found to be 70. Table 4 represents the citing patents (sorted by Publication Year) of the latest 3 years i.e. 2018-2020. Information about Citation patent count and NPL (Non- patent literature) citation count has been also indicated in the table. It is interesting to note that the papers are of significance for the patents being published very recently i.e. 2021.

Table 4. Patent Citing Scholarly Works (Research Papers) (2018-2021)

S.No.	Publication Year	Title	Cites Patent Count	NPL Citation Count
1.	2021	Method and system for disambiguating informational objects	15	12
2.	2021	Data processing method using neural network	3	2
3.	2021	Method and system for evaluating intellectual property	56	19
4.	2020	Scaling of log likelihood ratios (LLR) based on long training field (LTF)	27	6
5.	2020	Link association analysis systems and methods	46	17
6.	2020	Methods, systems and computer readable storage media for determining relevant documents based on citation information	40	1
7.	2020	Link association analysis systems and methods	49	19
8.	2020	Dynamic computer systems and uses thereof	203	30
9.	2020	Email conversation management system	237	152
10.	2020	Systems and methods for re-ranking displayed conversations	236	152
11.	2019	Paper text similarity detection method based on citation network	3	3
12.	2019	Method for analyzing technological documents using Bayesian networks	9	46
13.	2019	Link association analysis systems and methods	41	13

14.	2019	System and method for detecting and forecasting the emergence of technologies	24	24
15.	2019	Dynamic computer systems and uses thereof	157	19
16.	2019	Displaying conversations in a conversation-based email system	236	152
17.	2018	Link association analysis systems and methods	38	12
18.	2018	Link association analysis systems and methods	36	12
19.	2018	Producing a ranking for pages using distances in a web-link graph	67	721
20.	2018	Calendarizing location-based events and associated travel	74	16
21.	2018	Compensating for bias in search results	58	127
22.	2018	Way-finding method and equipment based on base classifier, and storage equipment	3	6
23.	2018	Compensating for individualized bias of search users	58	127

Fig. 7. Patent Count

The highest number of patent citations (10) for published in the Scientometrics were noted for the year 2015 followed by 8 in 2017, 7 in 2018 and again in 2020. There were 6 patents citing LIS research published in Scientometrics journal in 2019 while it accounted for 3 in the year 2021 (Fig.7).

4.2.4 Jurisdiction, Organisations and Domains:

From the result it can be noted that the highest number of such patents are from United States of America (66.81%) followed by China (24.3%), Korea (2.2%) and European Patent Office (2.2%) (Fig. 8). It is important to mention that 4.5% of these patents were attributed to WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organization).

Fig. 8. Patent Jurisdiction

The organisations applying and adopting LIS research for innovations in the form of patents include prominent companies like Google, Microsoft, Harrison and Auerbach etc. (Fig.9).

Fig. 9. Visualisation of the Citing Patent Organisations

5. Conclusion:

The evidence based approach followed by the study successfully answers the research questions. Out of 5651 DOIs of articles published in the journal *Scientometrics* 39 have been cited by 62 citing patents. The highest patent count (10) was noted in the year 2015 while in the first half (January-June) of 2021 witnessed 3 patents citing LIS research. Highest number of patents having linkages with LIS research were from US jurisdiction (66.81%) while Google LLC remains the top organisation utilising LIS research in filing patents. Thus the findings reveal that LIS research articles are valued by patents for their novelty and innovations essential for the progress and development of the society. The organisation which have used the LIS research in their R&D and have filed/granted these patents include Google, Microsoft, Harrison etc.

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